

OSeCOOLING: An Open-Source Energy System Model for Cooling Technology and Refrigerant Optimization Under Kigali Amendment Constraints

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Abstract

Cooling-sector decarbonization requires simultaneous management of two levers: refrigerant choice and equipment efficiency, but these levers have not previously been co-optimized within an open-source ESOM framework. This paper presents OSeCOOLING, an OSeMOSYS-based open-source model in which the optimizer selects cooling technologies endogenously across refrigerants (R-410A, R-32, R-290 and others) under a binding CO₂-equivalent constraint that integrates direct refrigerant emissions with indirect emissions from electricity, diesel and gasoline. The model is demonstrated for Costa Rica under four scenarios: (S1) Baseline with current technology mix, (S2) Kigali Amendment phasedown, (S3) Proactive Policy adding a 22% capital subsidy for heat pumps, and (S4) a Fossil Grid extension applying the same Kigali constraint as S2 but with a Central American average fossil-grid emission factor, used to test how grid carbon intensity reshapes the cost-optimal compliance pathway. The S4 result is the headline finding: when the grid is fossil-dominated, indirect electricity emissions dominate the total emission profile even under full Kigali compliance, showing that refrigerant phasedown delivers only a partial reduction of total cooling-sector emissions when not paired with grid decarbonization. S2 and S3 converge on near-complete R-290 heat-pump dominance by 2050, with subsidies acting as cost-reducers of the transition. OSeCOOLING is released open-source on GitHub, and the framework can be applied to multiple case studies.

Keywords: *cooling; refrigerant; OSeMOSYS; Kigali Amendment; open-source model; RAC sector; heat pump; R-290; Costa Rica*

1. Introduction

1.1 The cooling sector challenge

The global stock of air conditioning units is projected to grow from approximately 2 billion today to 5.6 billion by 2050 [1], [2], driven by rising temperatures, urbanization, and income growth across the Global South [3], [4]. Cooling appliances already account for nearly 20% of global electricity use in buildings [3], and without intervention, both energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from space cooling will continue to increase across all socioeconomic pathways [5], [6]. The recent finding by Zhang et al. [7] that cumulative air-conditioning-related emissions could reach 113 GtCO_{2e} by 2050 under a business-as-usual scenario, adding 0.05°C to global mean temperature, shows that the cooling sector is no longer a marginal concern in climate mitigation.

The challenge is intensified by the dual nature of cooling-sector emissions. Direct emissions arise from the leakage and end-of-life release of refrigerant gases, many of which are hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) with global warming potentials hundreds to thousands of times greater than CO₂. Indirect emissions result from the electricity, diesel, or gasoline consumed to power cooling equipment. The UNEP/IEA Cooling Emissions and Policy Synthesis Report [8] estimates that close to 75% of avoidable cooling-sector emissions come from energy efficiency improvements and 25% from HFC phasedown. Sherman et al. [9] projected that electricity for cooling in poorer countries could approach 75% of current total annual demand by mid-century, with regional pressures concentrated in tropical and subtropical economies. The World Bank's assessment of extreme urban heat in Latin America and the Caribbean [10] documents this pressure for the region in which Costa Rica sits, where cooling demand growth interacts with rapid urbanization and an already-warming climate.

The Kigali Amendment to the Montreal Protocol [11], adopted in 2016 and in force since 2019, mandates a phasedown of HFC production and consumption targeting an 80–85% reduction by 2047. For Article 5 developing countries, the schedule begins with a freeze in 2024 and proceeds through stepwise reductions. Identifying the best path for the replacement and technology mix of cooling sector is impossible without optimization, however, the industry still does not have an open-source tool capable of balancing these two emission sources simultaneously, leaving a void in climate strategy.

1.2 Literature review and research gap

Three adjacent research communities have produced sophisticated tools that, collectively, should enable cooling-sector optimization, but none has built the model that connects them.

On the demand side, global climate-driven demand modelling has advanced considerably since Isaac and van Vuuren [12] developed the first systematic global residential heating-and-cooling demand model accounting for climate change. Gi et al. [13] extended that work with cost-effective consumption estimates across countries and income groups, and the IEA Future of Cooling report [2] projected a near-tripling of cooling energy demand by 2050 under business-as-usual. Demand.ninja [1] now generates hourly heating and cooling demand at any spatial scale and the MESSAGEix-Buildings/CHILLED framework [5], [14] links climate-driven demand to an integrated assessment model at global scale. Falchetta et al. [3] characterized cooling inequality across emerging economies, Mastrucci et al. [6] mapped the future cooling gap across shared socioeconomic pathways, and Bezerra et al. [15] quantified the impact of warming on Brazilian household cooling demand. Lizana et al. [16], produced a global gridded dataset of heating- and cooling-degree-days under SSP–RCP scenarios. None of these tools, however, produces the technology- and refrigerant-disaggregated demand inputs required by a cooling-sector optimization model. They answer how much cooling? but not with which equipment, using which refrigerant, at what cost?

On the energy system modelling side, OSeMOSYS [17], [18] and its derivatives (OSeMOSYS-CR [19], OSeMOSYS Global [20], and CLEWs-based models [21]) underpin electricity and transport planning, while TIMES [22], MESSAGE [23], and GCAM [24] dominate power-sector decarbonization analyses. None of them targets the cooling sector. Leibowicz et al. [25] offers the most technology-disaggregated cooling representation in any optimizer, with five to seven options for a single American city and no refrigerant dimension. Zhang et al. [7] used GCAM to model AC-related GHG feedback loops but treated HFC emissions as aggregates. Even MESSAGEix handles refrigerant mitigation in a separate non-CO₂ accounting layer, decoupled from the technology competition that determines cooling service delivery [23]. Welsch et al. [26] extended OSeMOSYS with smart-grid functionality, demonstrating the framework's adaptability to demand-side and storage representation. Byers et al. [27] developed a flexible emulation of the warming–cooling feedback within MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM, but at aggregate cooling demand resolution rather than technology-level detail. Fodstad et al. [28] surveyed the broader frontier of

energy system modelling challenges, noting that end-use sector disaggregation remains an open problem. Across this body of work, refrigerant choice is never treated as an endogenous decision variable, which is the gap OSeCOOLING is designed to fill.

On the Kigali compliance side, the IIASA GAINS framework [29] quantifies HFC emissions and efficiency co-benefits across 162 countries. National Cooling Action Plans [30] supply bottom-up market projections, Hillbrand et al. [31] modelled Indian phasedown trajectories, and Hu et al. [32] evaluated global trajectories and argued that faster phasedown costs less overall. Country level cooling action plans illustrate the structured approach: India's ICAP [33] is the most comprehensive national-level integrated cooling strategy, and the AEEE/BEE national demand assessment [34] complements it with bottom-up efficiency-potential analysis. Dreyfus et al. [35] placed HFC mitigation in a broader climate disruption framework. For Costa Rica, the World Bank [36] produced a techno-economic analysis of AC efficiency regulations, and the GIZ Cool Contributions project [37] piloted R-290 split AC units and trained technicians. All this work relies on scenario-based accounting instead of optimization, which can add value to the methodology.

1.3 Paper objective and contributions

This paper presents OSeCOOLING, an open-source OSeMOSYS-based system optimization model purpose-built for the RAC sector. The model determines the least-cost portfolio of cooling technologies that satisfies sectoral demand under a binding cap on direct HFC emissions following the Kigali Amendment phasedown schedule while simultaneously tracking indirect emissions from electricity, diesel, and gasoline. The optimizer evaluates equipment type, refrigerant, and efficiency tier as competing pathways within a single cost-minimization framework. It operates, within an open-source dynamic optimization framework, a bottom-up sectoral characterization of Costa Rica's RAC sector built by applying the methodology for the creation of decarbonization and adaptation roadmaps for organizations [28]. OSeCOOLING extends earlier deterministic CBA/MACC analysis into dynamic, system-wide least-cost optimization with endogenous refrigerant choice.

The present work contributes to academic literature by:

- (1) Establishing an open-source ESOM that manages refrigerant choice as an endogenous decision variable for the cooling sector by selecting a technology, which implicitly selects a refrigerant with associated GWP, leakage profile, and direct emission trajectory.

(2) A sectoral demand structure covering domestic, commercial, industrial, retail and domestic refrigeration and transport cooling, with multi-fuel emission accounting that incorporates emission factors for electricity, diesel, and gasoline alongside direct refrigerant emissions. This enables the model to capture the interaction between grid carbon intensity and refrigerant choice.

(3) Demonstration through four policy-relevant scenarios for Costa Rica, a country with 2.6% residential AC penetration [26], a nearly 100% renewable electricity grid, and active R-290 pilot programs [37].

(4) Open-source release on GitHub, enabling adaptation to any country context with available demand data and technology cost parameters.

Costa Rica is used as a case study for the conceptualization of the model, it is not a full national assessment. With its low cooling footprint and nearly 100% renewable electricity grid, the country provides an ideal test case for showing how the model tracks both direct refrigerant and indirect energy emissions across the two-lever framework. The paper does not claim to produce definitive policy recommendations for Costa Rica, it demonstrates what a cooling-sector ESOM can reveal when both levers are co-optimized simultaneously.

2. Model Description: OSeCOOLING

2.1 Overview and design principles

OSeCOOLING is an energy system optimization model for the RAC sector built on the OSeMOSYS framework [17], [18]. It determines the least-cost portfolio of cooling technologies that meets exogenously defined sectoral demand over a planning horizon, subject to a total CO₂-equivalent emission constraint.

$$\min \sum_t [\sum_{tech} (CAPEX \cdot NewCap + OPEX \cdot Activity) \cdot DF(t)]$$

where t indexes years over the planning horizon 2025–2050, $tech$ indexes the technology set, $CAPEX$ (USD/kW) is the capital cost of new capacity, $NewCap$ (kW) is the new capacity built in year t , $OPEX$ (USD/PJ) is the operating cost per unit of energy service delivered, $Activity$ (PJ) is the energy service delivered by the technology in year t , and $DF(t)$ is the discount factor at a social discount rate of 8% per year. The objective minimizes total discounted system cost subject to demand satisfaction in each sector and timeslice, capacity–activity coupling, and the binding CO₂-equivalent emission constraint.

The model is designed around four principles. First, refrigerant choice is endogenous: each technology carries an associated refrigerant with a specific GWP, so selecting a technology implicitly selects a refrigerant and its emission profile. Second, emission accounting is comprehensive: direct refrigerant emissions, indirect emissions from electricity consumption, and indirect emissions from diesel or gasoline consumption are all included in the CO₂e constraint. Third, demand is structured by economic sectors (domestic, commercial, industrial, transport) rather than by system type, enabling alignment with national statistical data. Fourth, the model is open-source and released on GitHub with documentation, enabling adaptation to any country context.

2.2 Demand structure

Cooling demand in OSeCOOLING is organized into seven main pools sectors, each parameterized with a Specified Annual Demand (GBTU) and a SpecifiedDemandProfile, used to represent the distribution of demand among time slices:

- **Domestic:** Covers residential space cooling served by mini-splits, both inverter and non-inverter, window units, portable AC, and air source heat pumps, within the 2–18 kW range.

This is typically the fastest growing pool in countries at the onset of a cooling transition [3] [36].

- **Commercial:** Cooling demand in offices, retail, hospitality, and public buildings, served by rooftop units, VRF systems, small chillers, and commercial heat pumps in the 18–350 kW range.
- **Industrial:** Process cooling and cold storage, served by large chillers, ammonia-based systems, and CO₂ transcritical systems. industrial-scale heat pump technologies using these same natural refrigerants are also available as competing options in the optimizer
- **Food Retail Refrigeration:** The food retail pool covers centralized supermarket refrigeration systems and plug-in cases, which face distinct refrigerant constraints due to charge size and safety regulations.
- **Domestic Refrigeration:** Covers household refrigerators and freezers.
- **Mobile Air Conditioning:** For passenger vehicle mobile AC, primarily using R-134a or HFO-1234yf.
- **Transport:** For freight transport refrigeration and bus and truck AC, where R-404A and natural refrigerant alternatives compete.

Demand data is exogenous, provided as input from national statistics, market surveys and sectoral studies. For the Costa Rica application demand projections were constructed by applying the methodology in [38] to Costa Rica's RAC sector. RAC energy demand to 2050 was built by combining IPCC Tier-2 activity data, installed-unit counts, capacity per unit (in kW thermal / BTU·h⁻¹ / TR), and Energy Efficiency Ratio trajectories, with customs and import records to produce annual stock series. The resulting series were reorganized into the demand-pool structure defined above; projections are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demand projections for 7 subsectors for all scenarios.

Demand (GBTU)	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Domestic	9182.6	13517.4	16815.2	18776.1	20010.9	20412.6	21217.2

Commercial	1388.7	2596.6	3411.3	3899.2	4038.1	4256.6	4355.2
Industrial	1493.3	1985.5	2983.6	3477.2	3315.4	3660.7	3827.7
Food Retail Refrigeration	7913.1	10353.7	11115.1	12179.2	12213.6	12514.8	12526.7
Domestic Refrigeration	5505.5	6870.5	7434.1	7478.3	7738.2	7838.7	7962.5
Mobile — Passenger	11273.2	13228.1	15176.6	15843.2	16181.5	16245.9	16246.4
Transport	237.8	239.1	320.4	321.6	645.0	323.2	243.0

2.3 Technology representation

OSeCOOLING represents cooling technologies along three dimensions: equipment type, refrigerant, and efficiency tier. Each unique combination constitutes a technology in the OSeMOSYS sense, characterized by capital cost (CAPEX, USD/kW), fixed and variable operating cost (OPEX), efficiency (COP or SEER), operational lifetime (years), and a capacity factor.

Mobile Air Conditioning and Transport Refrigeration technologies are represented in OSeCOOLING with zero capital and fixed O&M costs. This is a deliberate modelling convention since the equipment cost of a vehicle-mounted AC system is bundled in the vehicle's CAPEX, which is accounted for in the transport sector rather than in the RAC sector. Including these costs in OSeCOOLING would therefore double-count expenditures already captured in the national transport ESOM [14].

The energy efficiency ratio (EER), which determines the electricity consumption required to satisfy a given cooling demand, differs between scenarios. The mitigation scenarios reflect improving import efficiency standards over time. The capacity for the activity unit (CAU) used throughout is 105.12 GBTU/kTR, and the availability factor is set to 1 for all technologies. Table 2 summarizes equipment types by subsector sector.

Table 2. Equipment types by subsector for OSeCOOLING

Sector	Equipment types	Typical capacity range
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Domestic	Self-contained units, ductless mini-splits (SSD), ducted splits (SCD), multi-split, rooftop units, air-source heat pumps (ductless and ducted)	2–18 kW
Commercial	Rooftop units, multi-split, AC chillers, heat pump chillers	18–350 kW
Industrial	Industrial condensing units, industrial centralized systems, process chillers, industrial heat pumps	>350 kW
Food Retail Refrigeration	Stand-alone units, centralized supermarket systems, commercial condensing units	0.5–100 kW
Domestic Refrigeration	Household refrigerators and freezers	0.1–0.5 kW
Mobile Passenger	Mobile AC for passenger vehicles, gasoline-driven, diesel-driven, electric compressor	2–8 kW
Transport	Mobile AC for buses and large vehicles, diesel-driven, electric compressor	5–20 kW

Each equipment type is available with multiple refrigerants where technically feasible, the full refrigerant catalog with GWP and Kigali status is reported in Supplementary Material. Heat pumps are represented as new build alternatives across the residential, commercial, and industrial pools, with ten technology entries spanning three tiers: ductless mini-splits in R-32 and R-290 at the residential and light-commercial level, R-290 and R-1234ze heat pump chillers at the commercial scale, and equivalent R-290 and R-1234ze options for large-capacity process cooling. Figure 1 shows the Reference Energy System with energy carriers, technologies, and final demands.

Figure 1. Reference Energy System diagram for OSeCOOLING modelling framework.

2.4 Refrigerant as endogenous choice variable

This is the central modeling innovation of OSeCOOLING. Refrigerant choice is implemented via parallel technologies that share a common demand pool but consume different refrigerant fuels, a modeling pattern enabled by OSeMOSYS's commodity structure. This application allows the optimizer to select among refrigerant options endogenously instead of treating refrigerant choice as a subsequent accounting step. The annual direct emissions from technology are:

$$E_{direct} = N \times C \times (L_{annual} + L_{EOL} / T) \times GWP$$

where N is the number of installed units (derived from capacity), C is the refrigerant charge per unit (kg), L_{annual} is the annual leakage rate (% of charge), L_{EOL} is the end-of-life loss rate (% of charge), T is the equipment lifetime (years), and GWP is the 100-year global warming potential of the refrigerant.

Refrigerant charge per unit (C) is reconstructed from the technology-level direct-emission inventory built by following the NDC Action methodology [38]. Charges are obtained using a reference-refrigerant approach, assigning a baseline charge to the dominant high-GWP refrigerants for each of the sixteen equipment classes, and charges for all other refrigerants in that class are derived by applying refrigerant conversion factors compiled from manufacturer specifications and the standards literature. Leakage rates follow IPCC 2019 Refinement default values [39]: $L_{annual} = 5\%$ and $L_{EOL} = 25\%$ for residential stationary equipment, $L_{annual} = 10\%$ and $L_{EOL} = 30\%$ for commercial and industrial refrigeration, and $L_{annual} = 10\text{--}15\%$ and $L_{EOL} = 40\%$ for mobile applications [39].

Each refrigerant fuel carries its own emission factor, so a cheaper R-410A mini-split with high direct emissions competes directly against a more expensive R-290 alternative with near-zero direct emissions, and the CO_2e constraint forces the optimizer to internalize a trade-off that previous work [8], [29] treated as a separate accounting exercise.

This formulation means that the Kigali Amendment phasedown schedule [11], can be implemented directly as an AnnualEmissionLimit on HFC-class emissions (this is an OSeMOSYS parameter used to cap total emissions in the model). As the constraint tightens over successive model periods, the optimizer endogenously shifts the technology portfolio toward lower-GWP

alternatives. The phasedown does not need to be translated into technology bans or market share assumptions, it emerges from cost minimization under an emission constraint.

2.5 Emission accounting

OSeCOOLING accounts for three sources of CO₂-equivalent emissions, which consists on:

(1) Direct emissions (refrigerant): Emissions from refrigerant leakage during operation and at end-of-life. For high-GWP refrigerants such as R-404A or R-410A, direct emissions can dominate total cooling-sector emissions, particularly in countries with clean electricity grids [8].

(2) Indirect emissions (electricity): The electricity consumed by cooling technologies carries an emission intensity determined by the grid emission factor, this factor varies dramatically across countries and over time as grids decarbonize.

(3) Indirect emissions (fossil fuels): Mobile AC systems in internal combustion engine vehicles which consume gasoline or diesel. OSeCOOLING incorporates standard emission factors for these fuels, closing the gap between the conventional RAC sector and transport sector emission accounting.

The total CO_{2e} is the sum of all three sources. The emissions constraint applies to direct emissions only, but indirect emissions enter the optimization through their cost, so grid carbon intensity shapes the cost-optimal refrigerant choice even when not regulated directly.

2.6 Scenario design

The model is demonstrated through four scenarios, all applied to Costa Rica, designed to analyze the key drivers of cooling-sector decarbonization:

Table 5. Scenario design for OSeCOOLING modelling framework

Scenario	Grid assumption	Technology availability	CO _{2e} constraint	Purpose
S1: Base Case	Costa Rica actual (~99% renewable; near-zero grid EF)	All refrigerants including R-32	No emission limit applied. Existing equipment stock follows its natural retirement schedule based on technology lifetime	Showing the high emission trajectory under business-as-usual.
S2: Kigali Amendment	Costa Rica actual (~99% renewable; near-zero grid EF)	All refrigerants including natural refrigerants; heat pumps	Annual refrigerant emissions limit following the	Identifies the least-cost technology and refrigerant pathway

		available for residential, commercial and industrial sectors; investment rate constraints applied	Kigali A5 Group 1 phasedown schedule	to achieve Kigali compliance on a clean grid.
S3: Proactive policy	Costa Rica actual (~99% renewable; near-zero grid EF)	All refrigerants including natural refrigerants; heat pumps are available for residential, commercial and industrial sectors. Investment rate constraints relaxed by 50% relative to S2; heat pump capital cost subsidized	Annual refrigerant emissions limit following the Kigali A5 Group 1 phasedown schedule	Quantifies the additional system-cost reduction achievable under the same Kigali-compliant emission limit when heat-pump CAPEX is subsidized and deployment constraints are relaxed.
S4: Fossil Grid	Fossil-dominated grid mix (~180 kTon/CO ₂ e/PJ)	All refrigerants including natural refrigerants; heat pumps available for residential, commercial and industrial sectors; same investment rate constraints as S2	Annual refrigerant emissions limit following the Kigali A5 Group 1 phasedown schedule	Tests how grid carbon intensity reshapes the cost-optimal Kigali-compliance pathway.

Each scenario is run under CO_{2e} constraint levels, from unconstrained (BAU) to Kigali complaint limits. This produces a cost curve showing total system cost as a function of the emission constraint, revealing the marginal abatement cost of cooling-sector decarbonization and the constraint level at which technology mix transitions occur.

2.7 Costa Rica application data

Costa Rica serves as the demonstration case for OSeCOOLING, showing a residential AC penetration of 2.6%, with 97% of units being mini-splits and import volumes growing at approximately 9% per year [36]. The electricity grid is 99% renewable, dominated by hydropower with growing wind and solar contributions [19]. Costa Rica is an Article 5, Group 1 party to the Kigali Amendment [11], with an HFC freeze in 2024 and reductions through 2045. The GIZ C4 project [37] has provided field data with R-290 equipment.

Demand projections were constructed by applying the NDC Action methodology [38] to Costa Rica's customs and inventory data and reorganizing the result into the seven sector structure described in Section 2.2. Cost and performance parameters draw on the World Bank [36], EIA

equipment cost data [40], and GIZ C4 field performance data for R-290 equipment [37]. Specific values by technology are reported in the Supplementary Material. Grid emission factors are calculated from the national energy balance, and the fossil-grid sensitivity uses a blended emission factor representative of the Caribbean and Central American region. The Proactive Policy heat pump CAPEX of 2.190 MUSD/GBtu reflects a 22% reduction relative to the Baseline 2.808 MUSD/GBtu, consistent with EIA policy-driven learning rates [40] and the adoption of variable-speed compressors.

3. Results

The four scenarios analysis reveal two principal findings. First, on a fossil-dominated grid, Kigali-level refrigerant regulation alone is insufficient to achieve deep cooling-sector decarbonization, due to indirect electricity emissions dominating total CO_{2e}, showing that refrigerant policy cannot offset them without accompanying grid decarbonization. Second, the technology transition pathway is robust to supply-side instruments: S2 and S3 converge on near-complete R-290 heat pump dominance by 2050 regardless of subsidy or deployment rate assumptions, with supply-side instruments affecting cost and timing but not the destination. The sections below present each scenario in turn, with S4 discussed last as the result with the broadest cross-country implications.

3.1 Demand characterization

As shown in Figure 2, Mobile demand constitutes the largest share of total cooling activity, declining from 30% in 2020 to 24% by 2050 as the vehicle fleet electrifies. Food Retail accounts for approximately 21% throughout the period, Residential space cooling grows from 25% to 32% under income, urbanization, and warming pressures, Domestic Refrigeration declines from 15% to 12% as appliance efficiency improves, and Commercial AC and Industrial cooling each contribute 4–7% and remain stable. Transport refrigeration represents a small share.

The overall demand structure shows that residential AC is the dominant growth driver and the primary candidate for refrigerant transition policy, and Mobile and Food Retail together account for nearly half of total cooling activity, making their technology and refrigerant trajectories central to any national emissions strategy.

Figure 2. Cooling demand shares by subsector for Costa Rica for all scenarios.

3.2 Transition to cleaner alternatives: Kigali Amendment (S2)

Under the Kigali Amendment scenario on Costa Rica’s case the optimizer shows a full substitution of conventional air conditioning technologies by heat pumps while meeting the demand. As seen in Figure 3, in the Baseline this demand is met entirely with conventional AC technologies alongside refrigeration and transport equipment. Under Kigali, the technology composition goes through a structural shift beginning in 2030, when heat pumps emerge as the cost-optimal alternative and begin displacing R-410A and R-32 conventional systems (Figure 4). Units that use R-290 are selected preferentially over R-32 because of its near-zero GWP, which reduces direct refrigerant emissions almost entirely. By 2040, heat pumps account for approximately 39% of of total cooling service delivered across all seven sub-sectors, corresponding to 58% of service delivered within the residential and commercial sub-sectors specifically. By 2050, conventional AC equipment is almost entirely displaced within those two sub-sectors. Mobile and Transport sectors remain structurally stable across both scenarios throughout the horizon, confirming that the

Kigali constraint in this model operates primarily through the AC sectors where technology substitution options are widest.

The 17% CAPEX premium associated with R-290 heat pumps (2.808 vs. 2.4 MUSD/GBtu against low-GWP conventional equipment) is offset within the model horizon by avoided direct emission costs, confirming that the Kigali constraint functions as an effective market signal for natural refrigerant transition on a clean grid.

Figure 3. Cooling service demand by technology under Baseline (S1), Kigali Amendment (S2), Proactive Policy Instruments (S3) and Fossil Grid (S4) for Costa Rica

Figure 4. Refrigerant transition under Baseline (S1), Kigali Amendment (S2), Proactive Policy Instruments (S3) and Fossil Grid (S4) for Costa Rica 2020–2050.

Emissions under both scenarios begin with indirect energy contributing 35–40% of the total in 2020 (Figure 5). Under Baseline, total annual emissions grow 73% peaking in 2040, driven by accumulating high-GWP stock, before declining as equipment retires. Under S2, direct refrigerant emissions fall from 2030 as R-290 heat pumps displace high-GWP equipment while indirect electricity emissions remain stable, producing a 74% reduction in total annual emissions by 2050 versus 2025 (79% compared to Baseline) through coupled refrigerant transition and efficiency gain.

Figure 5. Annual CO_{2e} emissions by source under all scenarios for Costa Rica 2020–2050.

3.3 Proactive Policy Instruments (S3)

The Proactive Policy scenario relaxes the maximum annual capacity investment constraints applied in the Kigali scenario and introduces a 22% capital cost subsidy on heat pump technologies, reducing their CAPEX to the same value as conventional low-GWP equipment. The scenario is designed to answer what additional benefits can be obtained under the same Kigali-compliant emission limit, but with supply-side intervention.

The technology mix mirrors S2 (Figure 3), where R-290 units replace conventional AC from 2030 and reach near-complete substitution by 2050. Relaxing technology-availability constraints does not produce a different portfolio, it reduces the cost of reaching the portfolio already set by the emission constraint. These results differ from behavioral barriers, refrigerant supply constraints, and installer capacity that would affect real-world deployment.

Regarding emissions, Figure 5 shows that while the technology mix and emissions at the end of the analysis are nearly identical across the Kigali and Proactive Policy scenarios, HFC emissions

under S3 are approximately 6% higher than S2 in 2030 and around 5% higher in 2035. This is due to deployment of heat pumps, while it is constrained under Kigali, the optimizer must more aggressively suppress investment in new high-GWP equipment in the early periods to stay within the emission limit. In the Proactive Policy scenario, the relaxed heat pump capacity ceiling gives the optimizer a credible low-GWP substitution pathway that can be deployed rapidly after 2030, and knowing that high-GWP equipment will soon be displaced, the optimizer tolerates a marginally larger residual R-410A stock in the 2030–2035 transition window without violating the emission constraint. In other words, relaxation does not directly permit more R-410A, it removes the near-term pressure to eliminate it. From 2040 onward, both scenarios converge to the same emission floor as the Kigali constraint tightens and legacy equipment retires.

3.4 Fossil fuel grid (S4)

The Fossil Grid scenario replaces Costa Rica’s near-zero grid emission factor with a value representative of fossil-fuel-dominated grids in the Caribbean and Central America based on IEA data (~180 kton CO₂e/PJ) [41], maintaining the investment rate constraints from the Kigali scenario and emission limits. This allows direct assessment of how grid carbon intensity shapes the cost-optimal technology pathway and total emission outcome, independently of any regulatory refrigerant constraint.

The technology mix follows the same path as previous scenarios (Figure 3) until 2040, after which heat pumps reach 43% of total cooling service delivered by 2050, compared with approximately 39% under S2 and S3. The additional adoption is concentrated on residential and commercial AC, where heat-pump alternatives are available. Sub-sectors without heat-pump alternatives (Mobile, Transport, refrigeration) are unchanged across scenarios. This additional capacity is driven by efficiency economics with the higher fossil-grid emission factor raises the effective cost of electricity consumption, making heat pumps competitive against conventional AC systems even absent a Kigali constraint. On a high carbon grid, efficiency-driven heat pump adoption emerges endogenously from cost minimization without requiring refrigerant regulation.

Figure 6 disaggregates the S4 emission profile into direct refrigerant emissions (left) and indirect emissions from electricity, diesel, and gasoline (right). Direct refrigerant emissions fall 74% between 2025 and 2040 under the combined effect of the Kigali constraint and the investment-rate constraints that limit retention of very high GWP legacy stock. The refrigerant composition shifts

from R-410A and R-404A in the early periods toward R-134a and, by 2045–2050, R-32, as lower cost conventional alternatives remain competitive against R-290 heat pumps once efficiency gains alone cannot close the cost gap, stabilizing direct emissions at 89% below the 2025 peak.

Figure 6. Annual CO_{2e} emissions by source (direct refrigerant and indirect electricity) under the Fossil Grid scenario (S4).

Indirect emissions which are dominated by electricity consumption rise by 26% between 2020 and 2025 and then remain broadly stable through 2050, declining by only 1.3% from their 2025 peak over the following 25 years despite the growing heat pump share. By 2040, indirect emissions account for over 90% of total sector CO_{2e}. The gasoline and diesel contributions are visible but secondary.

In a fossil-grid context, the emission profile of the cooling sector is determined by the carbon intensity of the electricity supply, not by the refrigerant portfolio. Refrigerant regulation, operating on the left panel alone, cannot produce deep total emission reductions while the right panel remains at this magnitude. In fossil-grid countries, grid decarbonization and efficiency policy are not merely complements to refrigerant regulation, they are prerequisites for it to deliver meaningful emission reductions.

3.5 Costs across scenarios

Figure 7 plots each scenario in cost-effectiveness space, with cumulative HFC emissions over 2025–2050. The Baseline scenario presents the highest cost and highest emissions, establishing the reference against which all scenarios are evaluated. All three scenarios fall in the cost-negative abatement zone, meaning they simultaneously reduce cumulative HFC emissions and total system cost relative to the Baseline, confirming that the cooling-sector transition is economically beneficial under all modelled conditions.

Kigali Amendment and Fossil Grid scenarios are nearly located, separated by only 36 MUSD despite their different grid contexts, while Fossil Grid achieves 11% deeper HFC reductions than Kigali due to stronger pressure on high-GWP refrigerants from the fossil grid emission factor. Proactive policy scenario presents a more beneficial place than the other two scenarios. Cumulative emissions are almost the same as Kigali scenario, but the total system cost is 464 MUSD cheaper, reflecting the capital cost reduction from heat pump subsidies. The figure demonstrates that Kigali compliance is not a cost burden but a cost opportunity, and that targeted equipment subsidies amplify the economic benefit without altering the emission trajectory.

The cost-effectiveness values reported in this section reflect the system-cost components endogenous to the RAC sector, which include equipment CAPEX and fixed O&M for stationary and refrigeration technologies. Vehicle CAPEX and fixed maintenance for mobile AC and transport refrigeration are excluded by design, as documented in Section 2.3, because they are accounted for in the transport sector.

Figure 7. Cost-effectiveness space for all four scenarios. X-axis: cumulative HFC-class direct emissions over 2025–2050 (Mt CO₂e). Y-axis: total system cost, discounted at 8% per year over the planning horizon 2025–2050 (USD billion).

Figure 8 plots the cost savings of each scenario relative to the Baseline expressed both as a percentage of total discounted system cost and in absolute terms. All three scenarios fall in the cost-negative zone, confirming that cooling sector decarbonization is economically beneficial under every modelled condition.

S4 achieves 5.5% savings, driven by efficiency-induced heat pump adoption rather than refrigerant regulation. S2 delivers a marginally larger 5.7% saving on a clean grid where the same heat pumps are pulled by direct-emission costs. The similar cost outcomes on opposite grid contexts indicate that the choice of policy instrument shapes the emission profile more than the cost outcome. S3 reaches 8.1% savings, reflecting the financial value of the 22% heat pump subsidy applied within the same Kigali-compliant framework, an additional 2.5% reduction in total cost over S2 for the same emission trajectory.

Figure 8. Cost savings relative to the Baseline scenario, expressed as percentage of total discounted system cost with absolute values in MUSD.

3.6 Comparison against observed baselines

The 2020 baseline output of the air-conditioning subsectors, is cross-checked against Costa Rica's most recent national greenhouse gas inventory as reported in the country's First Biennial Transparency Report under the Paris Agreement [42]. The inventory disaggregates IPCC category 2.F.1 (refrigeration and air conditioning HFC emissions) into stationary air conditioning, mobile air conditioning, chillers, stationary commercial and industrial refrigeration, and transport refrigeration. For the two air-conditioning sub-applications, the OSeCOOLING Baseline (S1) reproduces the inventory values closely, stationary air conditioning is modelled at 216.1 kt CO_{2e} against the inventory's 208.2 kt CO_{2e}, and mobile air conditioning at 156.6 kt CO_{2e} against the inventory's 169.0 kt CO_{2e}. The modelled refrigerant composition in stationary AC, dominated by R-410A consistent with the high-GWP equipment penetration documented by the World Bank [27], reproduces the constituent-gas composition reported by IMN under category 2.F.1 (predominantly HFC-32 and HFC-125, the components of R-410A blends).

4. Discussion

4.1 Main findings

The analyzed scenarios demonstrate that cooling-sector decarbonization is not a single-lever problem, the interaction between grid carbon intensity and refrigerant choice, which previous work [8], [29] has noted qualitatively, can now be quantified within a single optimization framework.

Under the Baseline scenario, total annual cooling sector emissions grow by 73% between 2020 and 2040 as the stock of high-GWP equipment accumulates, with direct refrigerant emissions dominating throughout and indirect electricity emissions declining from 35–40% of the total. The Kigali Amendment scenario (S2) shows that a binding CO_{2e} emission constraint is sufficient on its own to drive a full refrigerant transition with R-290 heat pumps progressively displacing high-GWP equipment from 2030 onward. This results in total annual emissions reaching a 74% reduction by 2050 relative to 2025, and a 17% CAPEX premium on R-290 heat pumps is offset within the model horizon by avoided direct emission costs. On a near-zero carbon grid, the refrigerant component is the larger share of avoided emissions, while the efficiency gain of heat pump technology is what makes the transition cost-competitive, delivering a 5.7% reduction in total discounted system cost relative to the Baseline. The Proactive Policy scenario (S3) confirms that the regulatory framework alone already identifies the cost-optimal technology pathway since S2 and S3 converge on a near-complete R-290 heat pump transition by 2050, with the 22% subsidy adding 464 MUSD in system cost savings (8.1% relative to Baseline) without altering the emission trajectory. The binding emission constraint is therefore the structural driver of decarbonization, financial instruments act as accelerants.

For Costa Rica specifically, the results extend the analytical foundation established by the World Bank techno-economic analysis [36] and the GIZ C4 pilot program [37]. Where the World Bank analysis evaluated scenarios through regulatory impact assessment, OSeCOOLING identifies the cost-optimal technology-refrigerant combination under a binding emission constraint, a fundamentally different question that accounts for the full interaction between equipment choice, energy source, and refrigerant GWP.

4.2 The model as a tool

OSeCOOLING fills a specific gap in the open-source modeling ecosystem: the OSeMOSYS family includes models for electricity supply [20], transport [19], and cross-sectoral nexus analysis [21], but no model for the cooling sector, and Kigali compliance tools like GAINS [29] provide accounting but not optimization. OSeCOOLING was designed to be straightforward to adapt to other country contexts, which can be achieved through the growing modelling community [43]. A practitioner adapting the model needs four inputs: sectoral cooling demand data (from national energy balances or market surveys), technology cost and performance parameters (from manufacturer data or techno-economic studies), a grid emission factor, and the country's Kigali Amendment phasedown schedule. The sectoral demand structure, modular technology catalog, and adjustable CO_{2e} emission constraint transfer directly across country contexts without modification.

In the specific analyzed case, the Fossil Grid scenario illustrates the model's generalizability beyond Costa Rica's specific context. By replacing the near-zero grid emission factor with the Caribbean/Central American average fossil grid intensity, S4 reveals a structural inversion of the cooling-sector emission profile: indirect electricity emissions dominate throughout, accounting for over 90% of total sector CO_{2e} by 2040, while direct refrigerant emissions, the central concern of Kigali compliance, become climatically secondary. The policy implication is direct that in fossil-grid countries, efficiency regulation and grid decarbonization must operate alongside refrigerant phasedown. The model quantifies this interaction, which is precisely the analytical gap that OSeCOOLING was designed to close. A further finding from S4 is that efficiency driven heat pump adoption emerges endogenously from cost minimization on a high-carbon grid, reaching 43% of total cooling service delivered by 2050 (sector total), without requiring additional refrigerant regulation.

4.3 Limitations

The limitations discussed in this section refer to the scope of the present Costa Rica application not to the OSeCOOLING framework itself. OSeMOSYS-based ESOMs accommodate finer temporal resolution, endogenous demand coupling, learning curves, supply-side constraints, and subnational spatial disaggregation. The present application does not exercise these capabilities, primarily because the disaggregated input data required to populate them is not currently available for Costa Rica.

A partial back-cast of the 2020 baseline against Costa Rica's national greenhouse gas inventory [42] is reported in Section 3.6, confirming that the stationary and mobile air-conditioning sub-sectors reproduce the inventory values within $\pm 10\%$. A formal back-cast across the full set of IPCC 2.F.1 sub-applications together with yearly tracking against the Montreal Protocol Country Programme HFC import records over the 2010–2024 period, is identified as a needed methodological extension.

Demand projections were constructed by the authors by applying the methodology in [38] to Costa Rica's RAC sector, drawing on Tier-2 activity data, stock dynamics, and EER trajectories rather than on climate variables. In this specific analysis there is not a formal sensitivity analysis over the demand growth assumptions used. If cooling growth diverges from the assumed trajectory, due to income shocks, climate acceleration, or policy-driven efficiency gains, the technology and emission trajectories reported here will shift accordingly. Sensitivity analysis over demand growth is identified as a priority extension.

The model does not estimate cooling demand from climate data, it takes demand as an input. The OSeMOSYS framework supports coupling with climate-driven endogenous demand projections. This extension is framed as a priority direction for future research, not as a limitation of the current work.

The framework supports trajectory inputs for technology costs and accommodates learning curves when supported by empirical data, but there is an absence of validated CAPEX trajectories for R-290 heat pumps in the Latin American market, in this case costs are held constant across the horizon

Finally, the availability of disaggregated demand and load shape data for Costa Rica does not allow the model to operate at the best temporal resolution. Sub-annual resolution (hourly or daily) is supported by the OSeCOOLING framework and would allow representation of peak-load dynamics, diurnal cycling, and cooling–PV interaction if needed.

4.4 Future research

OSeCOOLING is designed as a foundation for analysis under different case studies. The modular structure of OSeMOSYS, where demand pools, technology sets, and emission accounting are

defined as inputs, means that the framework can be extended along several research threads, each of which constitutes a substantive follow-up contribution.

The first extension concerns data centre cooling, an emerging demand class structurally absent from current cooling-sector models. Data centre energy use, which efficiency gains had temporarily decoupled from workload growth [44] is now rising rapidly under AI and machine-learning training workloads [45], with compounding water–energy trade-offs [46] that OSeCOOLING's multi-emission accounting framework could naturally accommodate. The refrigerant landscape for data centres differs substantially from building HVAC since liquid immersion cooling, two-phase systems, and large industrial chillers using ammonia or CO₂ are increasingly relevant, and the trade-offs between refrigerant GWP, water consumption, and energy efficiency differ from those in space cooling. OSeCOOLING's modular demand-pool structure could accommodate a data-centre pool with a tailored technology set, allowing the same refrigerant-endogenous optimization to be applied to this new demand class.

The second extension addresses the coupling between climate change and cooling demand, which the current model treats as exogenous. The S4 finding becomes substantially sharper when demand itself varies with warming trajectory. Lizana et al. [16] produced global gridded cooling degree day datasets, and Miranda et al. [47] quantified how those shift under warming from 1.5 °C to 2.0 °C, providing the climate-driven demand inputs that OSeCOOLING currently lacks. Coupling OSeCOOLING with these demand projections would replace the bottom-up Tier-2 demand series built for Costa Rica following [38] with endogenous climate-driven trajectories, enabling genuinely comparative regional analysis across tropical Africa, South Asia, Southeast Asia, and Latin America, regions that combine distinct climate trajectories, grid mixes, and AC saturation levels in ways that make the refrigerant–grid interaction particularly policy-relevant. This thread connects directly to the core finding of this paper: the policy prescription for a country on a fossil grid under a 3.0 °C trajectory is fundamentally different from that for a country on a clean grid under 1.5 °C, and a coupled model is the only tool that can make that distinction rigorously.

The third extension concerns the multi-scale gap between national energy system optimization and building-level design. OSeCOOLING operates at the national scale, determining the least-cost technology portfolio that meets aggregate sectoral demand. At the other end of the modeling spectrum, building energy simulation tools such as EnergyPlus and OpenStudio, together with the

urban building energy models reviewed by Reinhart and Cerezo Davila [48] and Ferrando et al. [49], resolve individual design decisions about envelope, glazing, orientation, and passive cooling that determine how much mechanical cooling a building requires in the first place. Hong et al. [50] identified the linkage between national-scale optimization and building-scale modelling as an open problem in urban building energy science. Bridging this gap represents important follow-up work in the modeling line, because it connects the optimization logic of OSeCOOLING to the physical and spatial determinants of cooling demand that no national ESOM currently represents.

Together, these three threads constitute a coherent research program: data centres extend the demand boundary to the fastest-growing new cooling class; climate coupling replaces exogenous demand with endogenous warming-driven projections; and multi-scale linking extends the modeling stack downward to building and urban design. Each thread is a separate paper; this one provides the open-source optimization core on which all three build.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented OSeCOOLING, an open-source energy system optimization model built for the cooling sector with endogenous refrigerant choice, determining the least-cost portfolio of cooling technologies across seven sub-sectors under a total CO₂-equivalent constraint encompassing direct refrigerant emissions and indirect emissions from electricity, diesel, and gasoline.

Demonstrated for Costa Rica across four scenarios, three findings stand out. The overarching result is that the relative importance of refrigerant policy versus efficiency policy is not fixed — it is determined by grid carbon intensity. This interaction is the central generalizable contribution of the demonstration.

On a fossil-dominated grid (S4), indirect electricity emissions account for over 90% of total cooling-sector CO_{2e} by 2040, overwhelming the gains achievable through refrigerant regulation alone. Kigali-compliant HFC phasedown reduces direct emissions by 74% relative to the 2025 peak, but total sector emissions remain high because the electricity component is unchanged. In fossil-grid countries, grid decarbonization and efficiency policy are prerequisites for refrigerant regulation to deliver meaningful total emission reductions, not merely complements to it.

On a near-zero carbon grid (S2) indirect emissions are almost absent, the binding Kigali constraint drives a near-complete transition from R-410A to R-290 heat pumps from 2030 onward, achieving a 74% reduction in total annual emissions by 2050 relative to 2025 (79% relative to the Baseline) through coupled refrigerant transition and efficiency gain.

The Proactive Policy scenario (S3) confirms that the technology destination is robust to supply-side instruments. A 22% heat pump capital cost subsidy and relaxed deployment constraints reduce total system cost by an additional 464 MUSD relative to S2, but do not alter the transition pathway. Within the model's cost and constraint assumptions, the regulatory framework is sufficient to identify the cost-optimal technology mix; financial instruments accelerate but do not redirect the transition.

Together, these findings demonstrate that OSeCOOLING moves beyond qualitative assertions by quantifying exactly how much each lever contributes to total cooling-sector emissions under each policy scenario, something previous tools could only describe in parts.

OSeCOOLING is released as open source on GitHub, with full documentation and the Costa Rica dataset. Future work should prioritize coupling with a climate-driven demand model for scenario analysis under warming projections, application to additional countries at different stages of the cooling transition and with different grid characteristics, and the multi-scale extensions described in Section 4.4.

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